

Research Article

First derivative spectroscopic method for simultaneous estimation of mesalazine and rifaximin in synthetic mixture

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The present study was aimed to describe a simple, sensitive, rapid, accurate, precise and economical first derivative spectrophotometric method for the simultaneous determination of Mesalazine (MESA) and Rifaximin (RIFA) in synthetic mixture.

Methods: The derivative spectrophotometric method was based on the determination of both the drugs at their respective zero crossing point (ZCP). The first order derivative spectra were obtained in 0.01 N NaOH and the determinations were made at 329.20 nm (ZCP of RIFA) for MESA and 292.80 nm (ZCP of MESA) for RIFA. The linearity was obtained in the concentration range of succinate 10-50 µg/ml for MESA and 10-50 µg/ml for RIFA.

Results: The limit of determination was 0.321 µg/ml and 0.301 µg/ml for MESA and RIFA, respectively. The limit of quantification was 0.974 µg/ml and 0.912 µg/ml for MESA and RIFA, respectively. The mean recovery was 100.20 and 99.52% for MESA and RIFA, respectively. The method was found to be simple, sensitive, accurate and precise and was applicable for the simultaneous determination of MESA and RIFA in synthetic mixture. The results of analysis have been validated statistically and by recovery studies.

Conclusions: The method was successfully applied to pharmaceutical synthetic mixture which is considered in approved patent which show no interference. The result of analysis has been validated statistically and by recovery studies. So, this method accurate, precise, robust, rugged and economic in nature.

Keywords: Mesalazine, Rifaximin, First order derivative method, Spectroscopic method

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Introduction

Mesalazine (MESA) and Rifaximin (RIFA) use for Inflammatory Bowel Disease. MESA is used as in anti-inflammatory agent, steroidal.

Rifaximin is used in Gastrointestinal Agents, Anti-infective agent. The use of Rifaximin in combination with MESA has been proved to provide beneficial effect in inflammatory bowel disease. The mechanism of MESA and RIFA is quite different. MESA and RIFA are two

different types of drugs offering some symptomatic relief to the IBD patients. MESA treats inflammation, whereas, RIFA reduces bio burden. MESA and RIFA novel combination used in treatment of inflammatory bowel disease Patented by Lupin Ltd, WIPO WO2009047801 A1.¹

MESA

Figure 1: Chemical structure of MESA.

MESA is a salicylate, its therapeutic effect does not appear to be related to cyclooxygenase inhibition; indeed, traditional non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs actually may exacerbate inflammatory bowel disease. Although the mechanism of action of MESA is not fully understood, it appears to be topical rather than systemic. Mucosal production of Arachidonic acid metabolites, both through the cyclooxygenase pathways, i.e., prostanoids, and through the lipoxygenase pathways, i.e., leukotrienes and hydroxyeicosatetraenoic acids, is increased in patients with chronic inflammatory bowel disease, and it is possible that MESA diminishes inflammation by blocking cyclooxygenase and inhibiting prostaglandin production in the colon. MESA appears to diminish inflammation by inhibiting cyclooxygenase and lipoxygenase, thereby decreasing the production of prostaglandins, and leukotrienes and hydroxyeicosatetraenoic acids (HETs) respectively. It is also believed to act as a scavenger of oxygen-derived free radicals, which are produced in greater in patients with IBD.²

MESA is chemically 5-Amino-2-Hydroxybenzoic acid. It appears as off white to gray, having molecular weight 153.14 g/mol.³⁻⁵

RIFA

Figure 2: Chemical structure of RIFA.

Rifaximin is a semisynthetic, rifamycin-based non-systemic antibiotic, meaning that the drug will not pass the gastrointestinal wall into the circulation as is common for other types of orally administered antibiotics. It is used to treat diarrhea caused by *E. coli*. Rifaximin acts by inhibiting RNA synthesis in susceptible bacteria by binding to the beta-subunit of bacterial deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA)-dependent ribonucleic acid (RNA) polymerase enzyme. This results in the blockage of the translocation step that normally follows the formation of the first phosphodiester bond, which occurs in the transcription process.⁶

Rifaximin is chemically (7S,9E,11S,12R,13S,14R,15R,16R,17S,18S,19E,21Z)-2,15,17,36-tetrahydroxy-11-methoxy-3,7,12,14,16,18,22,30-octamethyl-6,23-dioxo-8,37-dioxo-24,27,33-triazahexacyclo[23.10.1.1^{4,7}.0^{5,35}.0^{26,34}.0^{27,32}] heptatriaconta 1,3,5(35),9,19,21,25(36),26(34),28,30,32-undecaen-13-yl acetate. It is a Red Orange Crystalline Powder having molecular weight 785.87 g/mol.^{7,8}

The review of literature regarding quantitative analysis of MESA and Rifaximin revealed that no Simultaneous Equation method attempt was made to develop analytical methods for MESA and RIFA. Some spectrometric methods and chromatographic methods have been reported for the estimation of the individual and combination of drugs. The focus of the present study was to develop and validate a rapid, stable, specific, and economic Spectroscopic method for the estimation of MESA and RIFA in synthetic mixture.

Theory⁹

We can find out concentration of both the drug from combination mixture using the linearity equation. In this method using the absorbance of both the drug and mixture at their wavelength and put this value in following equation and we can find out the concentration of drugs present in combination.

$$Y = mx + c \text{ ----- (1)}$$

Where,

Y = Absorbance

m = Slope

x = Concentration

c = Intercept

Materials and Methods

Apparatus

A double beam UV/Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu model 2450, Japan) with spectral width of 2 nm, 1 cm quartz cells was used to measure absorbance of all the solutions. Spectra were automatically obtained by UV-Probe system software.

An analytical balance (Sartorius CD2250, Gottingen, Germany) was used for weighing the samples.

Sonicator (D120/2H, TRANS-O-SONIC), Class 'B' volumetric glassware were used (Borosilicate), all instruments and glass wares were calibrated.

Reference samples

MESA and RIFA reference standard were supplied by CTX Life Sci. Sachin, Surat and Lupin LTD, Ankleshwar as a gift sample respectively.

Materials and reagents

Methanol AR Grade (FINAR), Distilled Water, NaOH AR Grade (RANCHEM), Distilled water, HCl (ASTRON) was used for development purpose.

Preparation of standard solutions

Preparation of stock solution of MESA

Accurately weighed quantity of MESA 10 mg was transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask, dissolved, and diluted up to mark with 0.01 N NaOH to give a stock solution having strength 100 µg/ml.

Preparation of stock solution of RIFA

Accurately weighed quantity of RIFA 10 mg was transferred into 100 ml volumetric flask, dissolved and diluted up to mark with 0.01 N NaOH to give a stock solution having strength 100 µg/ml.

Preparation of standard mixture solution (MESA + RIFA)

4.0 ml of standard stock solution of MESA (100 µg/ml) and 1.0 ml of standard stock solution of RIFA (100 µg/ml) were pipetted out into two 10 ml volumetric flasks and volume was adjusted to the mark with 0.01 N NaOH to get 40 µg/ml of MESA and 10 µg/ml of RIFA.

Preparation of test solution

The preparation of synthetic mixture was as per patent.

Mesalazine – 800 mg
Rifaximin – 200 mg
Na.CMC – 544 mg
MCC - 416 mg
Mg. stearate - q. s.
Total= 2000 mg

From that powder equivalent to 100 mg of synthetic mixture in 100 ml volume flask dissolve in 25 ml 0.01 N NaOH. Sonicate for 15 min diluent up to the 100ml with 0.01 N NaOH and Shake Vigorously filter the solution. The solution was filtered and further diluted. 0.1 ml was withdrawn and made up to 10 ml that give 40 ppm and 10 ppm of MESA and RIFA respectively.

Methodology

The standard solutions of NIF (10 µg/ml) and MET (50 µg/ml) were scanned separately in the

UV range of 200-400 nm. The zero-order spectra thus obtained was then processed to obtain first-derivative spectra. Data were recorded at an interval of 1 nm. The two spectra were overlain and it appeared that MESA showed zero crossing at 329.20 nm, while RIFA showed zero crossing at 292.80 nm. At the zero crossing point (ZCP) of RIFA (292.80 nm), MESA showed a first derivative absorbance, whereas at the ZCP of MESA (329.20 nm), RIFA showed a first-derivative absorbance. Hence 329.20 and 292.80 nm was selected as analytical wavelengths for determination of MESA and RIFA, respectively. These two wavelengths can be employed for the determination of MESA and RIFA without any interference from the other drug in their synthetic mixture formulation.

First derivative conditions

Mode : Spectrum
 Scan speed : Fast
 Wavelength range : 200-400 nm
 Derivative order : first
 Scaling factor: 50

Results and Discussion

Selection of wavelength and method development for determination of MESA and RIFA

The standard solution of MESA and RIFA were scanned separately between 200-400 nm and zero-order spectra were not showed overlapping peaks.

Figure 3: Overlain zero order spectra of MESA and RIFA, respectively.

Thus obtained spectra were then processed to obtain first-derivative spectra.

First order derivative spectrum for MESA showed zero crossing point: 329.20 nm. The wavelength selected for estimation of MESA was 292.80 nm because it showed $r^2 > 0.999$ at this wavelength in mixture.

First order derivative spectrum for RIFA showed zero crossing point: 292.80 nm. The wavelength selected for estimation of RIFA was 329.20 nm because it showed $r^2 > 0.999$ at this wavelength in mixture (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Overlain first order spectra of MESA and RIFA.

Figure 5: Overlain first order spectra of MESA and RIFA in 4:1 ratios, respectively with the combination solution (4:1).

Validation of proposed method¹⁰

Parameters to be considered for the validation of methods are:

Linearity and range

The first-derivative spectra (Figure 4) showed linear absorbance at 329.20 nm (ZCP of RIFA)

for MESA (10-50 µg/ml) and 292.80 nm (ZCP of MESA) for RIFA (10-50 µg/ml) with correlation coefficient (r^2) of 0.9992 and 0.9993 for MESA and RIFA, respectively. This method obeyed Beer's law in the concentration range 10-50 µg/ml and 10-50 µg/ml for MESA and RIFA, respectively (Table 1). Correlation coefficient (r^2) from calibration curve of MESA and RIFA was found to be 0.9992 (Figure 5.1.2) and 0.9993 (Figure 5.1.3), respectively.

Figure 5.1.1: Overlain linear first order

Table 1: Calibration data for MESA and RIFA at 329.20 nm and 292.80 nm, respectively (n=6).

MESA(ZCP for RIFA 292.80nm)			RIFA(At ZCP for MESA329.20 nm)		
Conc. (µg/ml)	Absorbance ± SD (n=6)	%RSD	Conc. (µg/ml)	Absorbance± SD(n=6)	%RSD
10	0.065±0.0005	0.849	10	0.125±0.0001	0.824
20	0.172±0.0016	0.972	20	0.289±0.0012	0.419
30	0.303 ±0.0021	0.723	30	0.423±0.0039	0.931
40	0.414±0.0014	0.355	40	0.574±0.0027	0.475
50	0.537±0.0012	0.225	50	0.724±0.0025	0.345

spectra of MESA (Blue) and RIFA (Pink) in 1:1 ratio.

The regression line equation for MESA and RIFA are as following,

$$y = 0.0119x - 0.0576 \text{ for MESA} \quad (1)$$

$$y = -0.0148x + 0.0179 \text{ for RIFA} \quad (2)$$

From the combination solution of MESA and RIFA the dilution were made in ratio of 1:1 and absorbance were recorded (Table1) and correlation coefficient (r^2) of 0.9992 and 0.9993 (Figure 5) for MESA and RIFA, respectively.

Calibration curves for MESA

This series consisted of five concentrations of standard MESA solution ranging from 10-50 µg/ml. The solutions were prepared by pipetting out Standard MESA stock solution (1.0 ml, 2.0 ml, 3.0 ml, 4.0 ml, 5.0 ml) was transferred into a series of 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was adjusted up to mark with 0.01 N NaOH. A zero order derivative spectrum of the resulting solution was recorded and processed to first derivative spectra, measured the absorbance at 329.20 nm against a reagent blank solution (0.01 N NaOH). Calibration curve was prepared by plotting absorbance versus respective concentration of MESA.

Calibration curve for RIFA

This series consisted of five concentrations of standard RIFA solution ranging from 10-50 µg/ml. The solutions were prepared by pipetting out Standard RIFA stock solution (1.0 ml, 2.0

ml, 3.0 ml, 4.0 ml, 5.0 ml) was transferred into a series of 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was adjusted up to mark with 0.01 N NaOH. A zero order derivative spectrum of the resulting solution was recorded and processed to first derivative spectra, measured the absorbance at 292.80 nm against a reagent blank solution (0.01 N NaOH). Calibration curve was prepared by plotting absorbance versus respective concentration of RIFA.

Precision

Intraday precision

The data for intraday precision for combined standard solution of MESA and RIFA is presented in Table 2. The % R.S.D was found to be 0.157-0.506% for MESA and 0.211-0.464% for RIFA. These % RSD value was found to be less than ± 1.0 indicated that the method is precise.

Figure 5.1.2: Calibration curve for MESA at 329.20 nm.

Figure 5.1.3: Calibration curve for RIFA at 292.80 nm.

Table 2: Intraday precision data for estimation of MESA and RIFA (n=3).

Conc. (µg/ml)	ZCP of RIFA 292.80 nm	ZCP of MES 329.20
MESA + RIFA	Mean %RS D	Mean %RS D
10:10	0.065 0.157	0.124 0.464
30:30	0.301 0.506	0.426 0.234
50:50	0.534 0.285	0.722 0.211

Interday precision

The data for interday precision for combined standard solution of MESA and RIFA is presented in Table 3. The % R.S.D was found to be 0.024-0.330% for MESA and 0.211-0.468 % for RIFA. These % RSD value was found to be less than ± 1.0 indicated that the method is precise.

Table 3: Interday precision data for estimation of MESA and RIFA (n=3).

Conc. (µg/ml)	ZCP of RIFA 292.80 nm	ZCP of MES 329.20 nm
MESA + RIFA	Mean %RSD	Mean %RSD
10:10	0.062 0.024	0.123 0.468
30:30	0.303 0.330	0.425 0.359
50:50	0.535 0.285	0.721 0.211

Accuracy

From the synthesis mixture weighed accurately equivalent about 100 mg of RIFA. Four 100 ml Volumetric Flask was taken and in each flask added synthetic mixture equivalent to 10 mg of RIFA. Flask 1 formed as a *Placebo* and remaining flask 2, 3, 4 spike with 80, 100, 120%.of Solid API. The same procedure for MESA was repeated. Content in 100 ml volumetric flask dissolved in 25 ml 0.01 N NaOH and Sonicate for 15 minutes was taken and made up the volume with 0.01 N NaOH up to 100 ml. The solution was filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 42. With the Mesalazine & Rifaximin with the ratio 4:1 dissolved in 0.01 N NaOH with small volume of Solvent, Sonicate for 15 mins, then made up to 100 ml with 0.01 N NaOH with all excipients.

Now, this solution was used for further dilution.

Total amount of formulation was taken in 100 ml of volumetric flask and add 25 ml 0.01 N NaOH. 0.01 N NaOH was sonicated, filtered and made up to mark. From it 0.5 ml was diluted to 10 ml with 0.01 N NaOH of 0%, 80%, 100% and 120% solution this accuracy method done by spiking method. Data from nine

Table 4: Amount of API.

Amt. of API in synthetic mixture (mg)		Amt. of API Spiking (mg)		Total Amt. (mg)	
MESA	RIFA	MESA	RIFA	MESA	RIFA
40	10	-	-	40	10
40	10	32	8	72	18
40	10	40	10	80	20
40	10	48	12	88	22

Table 5: Recovery data of MESA and RIFA (n=3).

Level of recovery	Total Conc. (µg/ml)		Result of recovery study					
	MESA	RIFA	Total Quantity Found (µg/ml)		% Recovery & %RSD			
			MESA	RIFA	MESA	RIFA	MESA	RIFA
0%	20	5	20.12	4.95	100.4	0.175	99.13	0.709
80 %	36	9	35.96	8.94	99.76	0.201	98.83	0.958
100 %	40	10	40.05	10.01	100.3	0.419	100.0	0.529
120 %	44	11	44.01	11.01	100.0	0.358	100.1	0.255
Mean of 3 Determinations					100.2	0.364	99.52	0.6354

Table 6: LOD and LOQ data of MESA and RIFA (n=10).

Conc. (µg/ml)		Avg. abs* ± SD (292.80nm) MESA	% RSD	Avg. abs*±SD (329.20nm) RIFA	% RSD
MESA	RIFA				
20	20	0.175 ± 0.001	0.659	0.292 ± 0.001	0.461
LOD (µg/ml)		0.321		0.301	
LOQ (µg/ml)		0.974		0.912	

determinations over three concentration levels covering the specified range was determined and % recovery was calculated. The % recovery values are tabulated in Table 5. The value of %RSD within the limit indicated that the method is accurate and percentage recovery shows that there is no interference from the excipients.

Limit of detection and quantitation

The LOD for MESA and RIFA was conformed to be 0.321 µg/ml and 0.301 µg/ml respectively. The LOQ for MESA and RIFA was conformed

to be 0.974 µg/ml and 0.912 µg/ml, respectively. The obtained LOD and LOQ results are presented in Table 6.

Robustness and ruggedness

The obtained Ruggedness and Robustness results are presented in Table 7. The %RSD value was found to be less than ± 1.0 indicated that the method is precise. No significant changes in the spectrums were observed, proving that the developed method is rugged and robust.

Table 7: Robustness and Ruggedness data of MESA and RIFA (n=3).

Parameters		MESA (ZCP of RIFA 292.80nm)		RIFA (ZCP of MESA 329.20nm)	
		Mean	%RSD	Mean	%RSD
ROBUSTNESS					
Different instrument	Inst. 1	0.174	0.876	0.292	0.342
	Inst. 2	0.176	0.568	0.290	0.526
Different Analyst	Analyst 1	0.175	0.871	0.291	0.523
	Analyst 2	0.176	0.866	0.290	0.344
RUGGEDNESS					
Change wavelength	292.60&293.00nm	0.189	0.806	0.307	0.497
	329.00&329.40nm	0.195	0.780	0.277	0.550
Change Ratio	1:1	0.175	0.871	0.292	0.342
	4:1	0.416	0.366	0.290	0.525
	1:4	0.175	0.571	0.578	0.173
Solvent change	0.0098N NaOH	0.176	0.465	0.168	0.465
	0.02 N NaOH	0.186	0.809	0.184	0.655

Table 8: Analysis data of commercial formulation*(n=3).

Sr. No.	Formulation (synthetic mixture)		Absorbance* (292.80nm) MESA	% Assay MESA ±SD	Absorbance* (329.20nm) RIFA	% Assay RIFA ±SD
	MESA	RIFA				
1			0.418	99.63	0.166	100.70
2	40	10	0.417	± 0.30	0.165	± 0.70
3			0.416		0.167	

Application of the proposed method for analysis of MESA and RIFA synthetic mixture

As per the title of my topic the development and validation was done by synthetic mixture. So for that stable formula from the patent was selected and as per the ratio the synthetic mixture was prepared.

From that powder equivalent to 100 mg of synthetic mixture in 100 ml volume flask dissolve in 25 ml 0.01 N NaOH. Sonicate for 15 min diluent up to the 100ml with 0.01 N NaOH and Shake Vigourously filter the solution. & Filter the solution & further dilute. Withdraw 0.1 ml and make up to 10 ml that give 40 ppm and 10 ppm of MESA and RIFA respectively. From the spectra of assay's Zero order linearity of synthetic mixture converted to 1st Derivative

spectra (4DL 50SF) of concentration 40 µg/ml and 10 µg/ml for MESA and RIFA respectively.

A first order derivative spectrum of the sample solution containing 40 µg/ml of MESA and 10 µg/ml of RIFA was recorded and the absorbance at 329.20 nm and 292.80 nm were noted for estimation of MESA and RIFA, respectively. The concentration of MESA and RIFA in mixture was determined using the corresponding calibration graph. The % assay values are tabulated in Table 8.

Conclusions

All the parameters are validated as per ICH guidelines for the method validation and found to be suitable for routine quantitative analysis in pharmaceutical dosage forms. The result of

Table 9: Summary of validation parameters.

Sr. No.	Parameter	First order derivative method	
		Mesalazine	Rifaximin
1	Wave length Max.	329.20nm	292.80nm
2	Linearity (µg/ml) (n=6)	10 to 50 µg/ml	10 to 50 µg/ml
3	Regression equation	y =0.0119x-0.0576	y = -0.0148x+0.0179
4	Correlation coefficient (r ²)	0.9992	0.9993
5	Accuracy (%Recovery) (n=3)	100.20	99.52
6	Precision (%RSD)(n=3)	0.285-0.325	0.210-0.813
	Intra-day	0.283-0.497	0.210-0.359
7	Inter-day		
	LOD (µg/ml) (n=10)	0.321	0.301
8	LOQ (µg/ml) (n=10)	0.974	0.912
9	Robustness (%RSD)(n=3)		
	Change instrument	0.568-0.876	0.342-0.526
	Change Analyst	0.866-0.871	0.344-0.523
10	Ruggedness (%RSD)(n=3)	0.465-0.809	0.465-0.655
	Change Solvent	0.780-0.806	0.497-0.550
	Change in Wavelength		
11	Assay	100.50%	99.33%

linearity, accuracy, precision proved to be within limits with lower limits of detection and quantification. Ruggedness and Robustness of method was confirmed as no significant were observed on analysis by subjecting the method to slight change in the method condition. Assay results obtained by proposed method are in fair agreement.

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References

- Jahagirdar H, Badhe U, Thomas J, Kulkarni R, Kulkarni S, Therapeutic combinations

- and compositions for the treatment of gastrointestinal disorders .WIPO Patents WO 2009047801 A1, 2009.
- Mesalazine Drug Info. (Database available on internet): Drug Bank Available form: http://WWW.drug_bank.ca/drugs/DB00244. Accessed 25 Feb 2016.
- Mesalazine Drug Info. (Database available on internet): Drug Bank Available form: <http://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/5-Aminosalicylic%20Acid>. Accessed 25 Feb 2016.
- Mesalazine Drug Info. (Database available on internet): Drug Bank Available form: <http://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/5-Aminosalicylic%20Acid>. Accessed 25 Feb 2016.
- Mesalazine Drug Info.(database available on internet):Chemical book Available from: www.chemicalbook.com/productchemicalpropertiesCB1480481_EN.htm. Accessed 25 Feb 2016.
- Rifaximin Drug Info. (Database available on internet): Chemical book Available from: www.chemicalbook.com/productchemicalpr

- opertiesCB5244184_EN.htm. Accessed 25 Feb 2016.
7. Rifaximin Drug Info. (Database available on internet): Drug Bank Available form: http://WWW.drug_bank.ca/drugs/DB01220. Accessed 25 Feb 2016.
 8. Rifaximin Drug Info. (Database available on internet): Wikipedia. Available from: <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/rifaximin>. Accessed 25 Feb 2016.
 9. Davidson AG, Beckett AH, Stenlake JB. Practical pharmaceutical chemistry; 4th Edn; CBS Publishers, New Delhi; 2002: 275-300.
 10. International Conference on harmonization, Harmonized tripartite guidelines, Validation of analytical procedures, texts & methodology, ICH Q2 (R1).